

A Correlational Study of Occupational Stress and Professional Commitment among Nigerian Police Force Personnel in Kwara State, Nigeria

¹ IBRAHIM, Haruna, ¹ LASISI, Adekola Kamil, ²Aliyu, Salihu Kudumi

Corresponding author: iharuna800@gmail.com

¹ Department of Educational Management and Counselling, Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, Nigeria

² Institute of Governance and Development Studies, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19294486>

Abstract

This study investigated the correlations between occupational stress and professional commitment among Nigerian Police Force personnel, Kwara State, Nigeria. This study adopted a descriptive correlational research design. Three hundred and sixty police personnel were randomly selected from twelve police formations that were purposively selected. Two hundred and ninety-three instruments were returned useful. Police Stress Scale and Police Professional Organization Commitment Scale were adapted for data collection. Five Hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 significant level while PPMC and Multiple Regressions were used for data analysis. Findings revealed a significant relationship between Leadership Style and Professional Commitment ($r_{cal.} = 0.80$, $df = 291$, $p < 0.05$); also, there was a significant relationship between inadequate salary and professional commitment ($r_{cal.} = 0.74$, $df = 291$, $p < 0.05$); furthermore, there was a significant relationship between workload and professional commitment ($r_{cal.} = 0.82$, $df = 291$, $p < 0.005$). Independent Variables jointly contributed 88% of the variation which was significant ($AR^2 = 0.88$, $R_{=2/291} = 0.0069$ and $p < 0.05$). Leadership style made the highest relative contribution to the prediction of the dependent variable ($\beta = 0.93$), followed by inadequate salary ($\beta = 0.48$) and workload ($\beta = 0.08$) respectively. Based on the findings, it was recommended that, Nigeria Police adopts more effective leadership styles to enhance effective job performance by its personnel.

Keywords: Professional Commitment, Occupational Stress, Nigeria Police Force.

Introduction

Police personnel's professional commitment plays a crucial role in ensuring the protection of lives and property of citizens in Nigeria, particularly in Kwara State. Professional commitment of police personnel is a direct relationship between a personal belief and the goal of the profession, with greater congruency leading to greater individual efforts on behalf of the profession (Surnayo et al., 2024). Professional commitment can be referred to as a complex and dynamic relationship which glue an individual to his or her job, profession, calling or any other endeavor which usually involve alignment and agreement of one's core values with and that of organizational ethics resulting in willingness to contributing to such profession or organization positively through diligence, dedication and passion (Yusnita, et al., 2020). Professional commitment therefore could be said to mean a deep desire to put in valuable amount of effort and energy to achieving professional excellence, driven by enthusiastic willingness to actualize the goals, values, and ideals of an organization. In Kwara State, the personnel of the Nigeria Police force have shown worrisome deficiency in their commitment to their professional duties especially in ensuring the adequate protection of lives and properties (Adejumo et al., 2017). The indicators of occupational stress in this study include leadership style, inadequate salary and work load of police personnel in Kwara State.

The effectiveness of an organization's leadership style is an essential factor in determining the overall success, and the Nigeria police force is not immune to this principle (Ibrahim & Lasisi, 2023). Charged with the primary responsibilities of maintaining peace, enforcing laws, and safeguarding lives and properties, the police force's leadership has a direct impact on the security and well-being of Nigerian citizens, including those in Kwara State (Lateef, 2019). As an organization, the police sector has not been exempted from the pressure of achieving its goals. Effective leadership style and structures has been proposed by various scholars and researchers to be a prerequisite for achieving organizational outcomes. The Nigerian Police Force has experienced different leadership qualities, training and several reorganizations including purging it of deviant personnel, these efforts have not sufficiently transformed the force into a sufficiently friendly response, literate, largely honest, well equipped, numerable to sustain public confidence in any appreciable sense (Bakare & Aderinola, 2019).

The Kwara State police command is grappling with an unsustainable work load resulting from insufficient manpower. Consequently, police personnel in Kwara State police command are forced to work excessively long hours usually between twelve to twenty-four hours at a stretch. This has made the personnel to be assigned multiple duties simultaneously resulting in their inability to perform effectively. For instance, a police Personnel investigating a case may be abruptly reassigned to for salaries and escort duties or Very Important Person's (VIP) protection with such investigation placed on hold. It was also established that despite the inadequacy of man power, the police Personnel are not adequately motivated, with excessive duty hours and negligible financial allowance packages resulting in widespread dissatisfaction, particularly among the junior ranks. (Steffey et al., 2023). Prolonged working hours without adequate rest have a debilitating effect on the general health of every human being including police personnel. Inadequate can lead to loss of sleep, anxiety, psychological trauma and reduced job performance (Ibrahim & Lasisi, 2023). The Nigerian police force has persistently overlooked the importance of adequate rest and this has become a major occupational stressor among personnel of the Nigeria police force (Ugwuoke, et al., 2024). Furthermore, inadequate salary and staff welfare packages have a detrimental effect on police performance and organizational commitment.

Inadequate salary and other forms of staff welfare packages has a paramount negative effect on the personnel of the Nigeria police force at ensuring adequate performance and commitment to their official responsibilities. Hassan, et al. (2022) affirmed that there is a direct relationship between staff welfare and staff commitment among officers and men of the Nigerian police. Also, Nwatu and Nwatu (2020) supported this view by positing that there is a positive and progressive relationship between emolument and employee productivity. The amount of what an employee can offer in his or employment is to a large extent dependent on the nature and size of the salary payable to the employee. There is a direct positive correlation between employee's welfare such as adequate and prompt payment of salary and other motivational packages and effective service delivery.

The professional Commitment of Nigerian Police Force personnel are essential to the protection of lives and properties of all Nigerians. However, occupational stress resulting from enormous workload, poor leadership styles and inadequate salary can be a major impediment to professional commitment Nigeria Police Force personnel with dire consequence on the economic and political growth and

stability. Researchers have conducted studies on various aspects of the Nigerian Police Force emphasizing on different variables related to job stress and Professional and organizational commitment yet the problem has been persistence. For instance, Ibrahim and Lasisi (2023) studied the occupational stress among police personnel in Kwara State, Ejike, (2019) investigated the analysis of job characteristics influencing organizational commitment among police officers in Enugu, Nigeria among others. The challenges of lack of organizational commitment resulting from shortage of manpower, inadequate salary and emoluments, and ineffective leadership styles has remained persistent especially in Kwara State leading to poor job performance. Therefore, the researcher was interested to investigating the correlation between occupational stress and organizational commitment among Nigerian Police Personnel in Kwara State, Nigeria.

The main objective of the study is to examine the correlations between occupational stress and the professional commitment among employees of Nigerian police force in Kwara State. The specific objectives of this study are to;

1. Investigate the relationship between Leadership Style and professional commitment among personnel of the Nigeria Police Force in Kwara State.
2. Examine the relationship between Inadequate Salary and professional commitment among personnel of the Nigerian Police Force in Kwara State.
3. Determine the relationship between Workload and professional commitment among personnel of the Nigerian Police Force in Kwara State.
4. Analyze the joint contributions of occupational of independent variables to the prediction of Dependent variable.
5. Explore the relative contributions of independent Variables to the prediction of Dependent Variable.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance for the purpose of this study;

1. There is no significant relationship between Leadership Style and Professional Commitment among personnel of the Nigerian Police Force in Kwara State.
2. There is no significant relationship between Inadequate Salary and professional commitment among personnel of the Nigerian Police Force in Kwara State.
3. There is no significant relationship between Workload and professional commitment among personnel of the Nigerian Police Force in Kwara State.
4. There is no significant joint contribution of independent variables to the prediction of dependent variable.
5. There are no significant relative contributions of independent variables to the prediction of dependent variable.

Methodology

This study employed a Descriptive research design of correlational type. The population of the study consist all serving Nigeria Police personnel in Kwara State police command. Kwara State has four thousand, four hundred and twenty-eight (4,428) deployed across sixty (60) police divisions, eight (8) area commands and one state command (KWPPRO, 2023). Based on the population size of the study, the required sample size for the study is 351 police personnel (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970). However, to ensure equal representation across police formations in Kwara State, three hundred and sixty (360) police personnel were randomly sampled from twelve police formations which comprise of four police formation consisting of one Area Command and three Divisions per each of the three senatorial districts in the state. Purposive sampling was adopted in the selection of the police formations based on their strength (population). Research scales titled Police Perceived Organization Commitment Scale (PPOCS) by Aremu, (2009) and Police Stress Survey (PSS) Sielberger, (1981) were adopted and subjected to pilot testing to determine the suitability of the adapted instruments in researcher's locality. The adapted instrument consisted thirty (30) items that were relevant in the measurement of the sub variables of stress which were workload, inadequate salary and leadership style (independent variables) and another eight-item section measuring Organizational Commitment of the Nigeria police force. The instrument had four (4) point rating scale ranging from "disagree, to strongly agree". In getting the

instrument ready for use, fifty (50) copies of the instrument were administered on police personnel serving in Police Headquarters, Osogbo, Osun State Nigeria. The split half reliability method was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. The instrument returned reliability coefficient of Leadership Style ($r = 0.90$), Inadequate Salary ($r = 0.96$), Workload ($r = 0.95$) and Professional Commitment ($r = 0.92$). The study got the ethical approval and permission of the Kwara State police command through the commissioner of police. Copies of the instruments were also submitted to Kwara State commissioner of police for perusal and approval for administration on police personnel of the command. Multiple regression was used to test hypotheses four and five (4 &5) while Pearson's Products Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test hypotheses one to three (1-3). All hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: *Pearson Products Moment Correlations (PPMC) Table Showing the Relationship between Leadership Style (LS) and Professional Commitment (PC) among personnel of the Nigeria Police Force in Kwara State.*

Variable	No	X	SD	DF	r cal	Significance	P
LST	293	22.88	5.05	291	0.80	0.00	**
PCT	293	20.81	3.67				

** (Significant at 0.05 critical Region)

Table 1 shows the result obtained from testing hypothesis one. From the above table, it is shown that r calculated value = 0.80, degree of freedom = 291 and significant level = 0.00. Since the significant level is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is here by rejected. Thus, there is a significant relationship between LS and PC among personnel of the Nigeria Police Force in Kwara State.

Table 2: *PPMC Table showing the Relationship between Inadequate Salary and Professional Commitment among Personnel of the Nigeria Police Force in Kwara State.*

Variable	No	X	SD	Df	r cal	Significance	P
PCT	293	20.81	3.67	293	0.74	0.00	**
IS	293	30.22	4.97				

** (Significant at 0.05 critical Region)

Table 2 showed the result obtained from the testing of hypothesis two. From the above table, it is evident that r. calculated value is = 0.74, degree of freedom = 291 and significant level = 0.00. Since the level of significant is less than 0.05 the null hypothesis two was rejected. Thus, there was a significant relationship between inadequate salary and professional commitment among personnel of the Nigeria Police Force in Kwara State.

Table 3: PPMC Table showing the Relationship between Work Load and Professional Commitment among Personnel of the Nigeria Police Force in Kwara State.

Variable	No	X	SD	DF	r cal	Significance	P
PC	293	20.81	3.67	291	0.82	0.00	**
WL	293	28.02	4.50				

** (Significant at 0.05 critical Region)

Table 3 shows the results obtained from testing of hypothesis three (3). From the table above, it is shown that r. calculated value = 0.82, degree of freedom = 291 and significant level is 0.00. Since the significant level is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis three was rejected. Thus, there was a significant relationship between WL and PC among personnel of the Nigeria Police Force in Kwara State.

Table 4: Multiple Regression Table Showing the Joint Contribution of the Independent Variables to the predictions of Dependent Variable among Personnel of Nigeria Police Force in Kwara State.

Model	Sum of square	DF	Mean square	Adjusted R ²	Standard error of estimate	F. Calc.	Sig
Regression	3459.14	3	1153.05	0.88	1.29	696.9	0.00**
Residual	478.16	289	1.66				
Total	3937.30	292					

** (Significant at 0.05 critical Region)

Table 4 Shows the result obtained from testing hypothesis four. From the table, AR² = 0.88, standard error of estimate = 1.29. This indicated that the independent variables (Leadership Style, Inadequate

Salary & Workload) jointly contributed 88% of the variation to the dependent variable. This was confirmed by Anova table which returns 696.9 as F ratio value which is significant at 0.05

Table 5: *Regression Table showing the relative contributions of the independent variables to the Prediction of the dependent variable among personnel of the Nigeria Police Force in Kwara State.*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient	Standardized coefficient	Standard Error	Beta	t. cal.	Significance
	B		Standard error	Beta		
(Constant)	14.37		0.71		20.30	0.00**
LST	0.67		0.02	-0.93	43.19	0.00**
IST	-0.36		0.02	-0.48	-22.63	0.00**
WLT	0.07			0.08	3.87	0.00**

** (Significant at 0.05 critical Region)

Table 5 shows the result obtained from testing hypothesis five (5). From the table, it is shown that unstandardized B range from 14.37 to 0.07, standardized error ranged from 0.71 to 0.02, Beta value ranged from 0.93 to 0.08 and t-value ranged from 43.19 to 3.87. It is shown from results that leadership style has the highest relative contribution $\beta = 0.93$ to the prediction of professional commitment which is followed by inadequate salary with $\beta=0.48$ and workload $\beta = 0.08$ respectively.

Discussion of findings

The study investigated the relationship between occupational stress and professional commitment among personnel of the Nigerian police Force in Kwara State, Nigeria. The results obtained from testing the hypotheses revealed that there was significant relationship between Inadequate Salary and Professional commitment (r. cal. =0.74, df = 291, sig = 0.00) among Personnel of the Nigerian Police Force in Kwara State, Nigeria. This was supported by Bashir & Gani (2020) who posited that there a positive correlation between pay and job security and organizational commitment among university employees. Also, there was a significant relationship between Work Load and professional Commitment (r. cal = 0.82, df = 291, sig = 0.00). This was in agreement with Onyemah, et al. (2024) which revealed that there is a correlation between workload and organizational commitment among

staffers in universities. Furthermore, there was significant relationship between Leadership Styles and professional Commitment ($r_{cal} = 0.80$, $df = 291$, $sig = 0.00$). This finding was supported by Saykur, et al. (2020) which revealed a significant relationship between leadership styles and organizational commitment among lecturers in higher institutions.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that there is a significant relationship between the independent variables (Leadership Style, Inadequate Salary and Workload) and Dependent Variable (Professional Commitment) among personnel of Nigeria Police Force in Kwara State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. The Nigeria Police Force should adopt a more effective leadership style that will enhance effective job performance by its personnel in Kwara State.
2. Salary of Police Personnel should be increased to enhance organizational commitment Nigerian Police Force Personnel in Kwara state, and
3. More Police Personnel should be deployed to Kwara State Police Command to reduce the workload of personnel of the Nigerian Police Force personnel.

References

- Adejumo, A. O., Hammed, A. A., Ikoba, N. A., Job, O., Adeniyi, I. O., Oguntunde, P. E. & Akinrefon, A. A. (2017). A study of prominent crimes in Kwara state Nigeria. *Journal de la Scientifique de Universite de Lome*, 19(2), 547-558.
- Aremu, A. O. (2009). *Police Stress Scale and Police perceived Organizational Commitment Scale*. Spectrum Books Limited.
- Bakare, A. R., & Aderinola, G. T. (2019). The Nigeria Police and Internal Security Management in Nigeria. In: Oshita, O. O., Alumona, I. M., Onuoha, F. C. (eds). *International Security Management in Nigeria*. Palgrave Machmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-8215-4_20

- Bashir, B. & Gani, A. (2020). Testing the effects of Job satisfaction on organizational Commitment. *Journal of Management Development*, 39(4), 525-542.
- Ejike, A. O., Paul, I. O., & Uche, J. A. (2019). Contributions of job characteristics in Organizational commitment of police officers in Enugu urban, Nigeria. *Nigeria Journal of Psychological Research*, 9(1), 139-157.
- Hassan, U. U., Ojo, G. R. & Weyano, P. (2022). Effects of policies on employee job performance in Government Agencies: A case study of Federal Inland Revenue Service. *FUW-International Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 7(2), 27. <https://fuw-ijmss.com.ng/index-php/fijmss/article/vie/12>.
- Ibrahim, H. & Lasisi, A. K. (2023). Occupational Stress among Personnel of Nigerian Police Force in Kwara State: Counselling implication. *Al-Hikmah Journal of Education*, 10(2), 54-63.
- Krejcei, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30(3), 607-610. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001316447003000308>
- Lateef, A. (2019). *Exploring the factors responsible for occupational stress among police officers in Nigeria*. (A Doctoral Thesis, Walden University). proQuest Dissertations and theses.
- Nwatu, A. A. & Nwatu, A. C (2020). Relationship between Welfare benefits and Job Satisfaction among Primary Healthcare Workers in Nkanu West Local Government Area of Enugu State, Nigeria. *Esut Journal of Sociology*, 16(1), 65-81.
- Oyemah, T. A., Raji, N. A., Silvester, A. O., Adewuyi, H. O. (2024). Enhancing teaching productivity among University Staffers: the influence of organizational commitment and workload. *Journal of General Education and Humanities*, 3(1), 37-46
- Saykur, A., Susilo, T. A. B., Wike, W. & Ahmadi, R. (2020). Sustainability of communication, organizational culture, cooperation, trust and leadership styles for lectures' commitment in higher education. Budapest International Research and Critics Institute: *Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(2), 1325 – 1335.
- Spielberger, C. D., Westberry, L. G., Grier, K. S., & Greenfield, G. (1981). *The Police Stress Survey*. United State Department of Justice
- Steffey, M. A., Risselada, M., Scharf, V. F., Boute, N. J., Zamprogno, H., Winter, A. L., & Griffon, D. (2023). A narrative review of the impact of work hours and insufficient rest on job performance. *Veterinary Surgery*, 52(4), 491-504.
- Surnayo, W., Yusnita, N., & Radnawata, D. (2024). Examination of influences of personal

values and job satisfaction dimensions on professional commitment. *Cogent Education*, 11(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186x.2024.2364472>.

Ugwuoke, C. O., Stephen, M. O., Ugwuozu, M. I., Onah, V. C. & Akwaji, F. (2024). Police job stress, workload and burnout in Nigeria: The tired and frustrated cop. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, 0306624x241270558.

Yusnita, N., Surnayo, W. & Notosudjono, D. (2020). Professional commitment – organizational mechanism, individual characteristics and individual mechanism. *Zeszyty Naukowe Politechniki Czestochowskiej. Zarzadzanie*, 40(1), 67- 83

